

**ADVANTAGES OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN NON-LINGUISTIC
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Annotation: The article is devoted to open main advantages of teaching foreign languages in non-linguistic higher educational institutions. Moreover, ways and tasks of teaching foreign language in non-linguistic universities were noted.

Key words: *educational standard, patriotic, aesthetic, self-knowledge, English for Special Purposes, professional competencies, vocational training.*

Currently, a social order has been formed for a deep knowledge of a foreign language by citizens of our republic, there are such pronounced trends in foreign language education as the growth of the status of a foreign language (primarily English), the strengthening of the motivation for its study, the functional focus of language learning. The state educational standard of higher professional education requires taking into account professional specifics when teaching a foreign language, its focus on the implementation of the tasks of the future professional activity of graduates. Nevertheless, language teaching taking into account the professional orientation still remains unsatisfactory, and the level of professional foreign competence of graduates is low, not in line with modern requirements of society and the labor market, as evidenced by the results of studies of the state of teaching a foreign language in non-language universities, data from production, an acute shortage of specialists who have a certain register of foreign-language knowledge necessary for professional communication[1]. The main reasons for the insufficiently high quality of teaching a foreign language, taking into account the professional specifics of a non-linguistic university, are not only a small number of hours allocated for studying a foreign language, the lack of special training for foreign language teachers for non-linguistic faculties of universities, the low level of language education in secondary schools, but also the insufficient development of the methodology of teaching a foreign language in integrative connection with vocational training.

The educational component of teaching in a foreign language consists, in our opinion, in the formation of students' respect and interest in the culture and the people of the country of the studied language; fostering a culture of communication; maintaining interest in learning and

formation of cognitive activity; fostering the need for practical use of language in various fields of activity, including professional ones. In foreign language classes educational opportunities are implemented through the content of the materials used; methods and forms of teaching; the use of incidental and specially created educational situations; through the personality and behavior of the teacher. In setting the educational purpose of a foreign language lesson, the following aspects can be distinguished: moral, patriotic, aesthetic and personal. In scientific and pedagogical literature under moral education means "the formation of moral attitudes, the ability to improve them, the ability to act in accordance with social requirements and norms, a solid system of habitual, everyday. Moral behavior. teaching a foreign language has unlimited educational opportunities when a foreign language is used as a means of introducing students to the culture, history and traditions of not only their own country, but also the countries of the studied language. Learning a foreign language is also a way of self-knowledge and personal expression in the process of communication. Personal education occurs through work, study, communication and play. When teaching a foreign language, almost all forms of education are used because it is both a subject of instruction and a means of communication[2].

In a modern university, a teacher of English for Special Purposes has to spend a lot of time developing teaching materials for a number of reasons. In some cases, this is due to the lack of English textbooks for students of rare specialties, in others - the high cost of educational materials, in the third - their unacceptability for educational purposes in general or for a specific educational situation. The development of training materials can take place on the basis of an already existing program or simultaneously with its creation. One of the most important tasks of university education is the formation of ., Accordingly, the teaching of a foreign language for special purposes is dictated by the needs of professional communication. Modern requirements for higher education teachers provide for the formation of a new type of specialist - a personality with the ability for creative, independent activity and high professional qualifications[3]. Constantly changing social, political and economic conditions define new challenges and dictate the necessary changes focused on students, their real interests and needs. Foreign language competence ensures the readiness of the graduate to the practical use of skills and abilities obtained in a professional environment. Nowadays, most of the scientific and technical literature is published in foreign languages. Within the General information space, in the absence of knowledge of a foreign language, a modern specialist is available only the minimum necessary information from translated books, articles, reports in the field of professional knowledge. The aim of teaching a foreign language to students of non-linguistic specialties should be to achieve a level sufficient for its practical use in the future professional field. Vocational training takes

into account the professional nature of not only the content of the training materials, but also the activities that shape professional skills. A modern graduate of the University is no longer enough to be able only to read and translate specialized texts, but also to be able to use a foreign language in various fields of communication. Professionally-oriented foreign language training should be aimed at solving the following tasks:

1. Development of communication skills by types of speech activity (speaking, listening, reading, writing). Successful mastery of the skills of dialogic speech is the ability to conduct a conversation on various topics, share information of a professional nature. Monologue speech involves the ability to make a report, a message, to express your views in the discussion. The purpose of teaching listening is the formation of skills of perception and understanding of the interlocutor's statements in a foreign language, in accordance with a certain situation and the sphere of communication. The result of learning to read is the possession of all kinds of reading publications of various genres, including special literature. Objectives of teaching writing are skill compilation of abstracts, abstract of presentation, comprehension, translation and writing of business letters, contracts, etc.;
2. Mastering certain language knowledge (knowledge of phonetic phenomena, grammatical forms, rules of word formation, lexical units). Language skills are acquired throughout the course, as each topic or situation of communication is related to certain language and speech means;
3. the formation of socio-cultural knowledge that attach students to the culture of the native speaker of the target language, help to adapt to a foreign language environment, to avoid misunderstandings in communication. But the main thing is not memorizing the facts, but the ability to compare the socio-cultural experience of the people speaking the studied language with their own experience, with the cultural values of their country, which contributes to the formation of a common culture of students;
4. Mastering a certain set of units of professional vocabulary, special terminology in a foreign language. Learning the language of the speciality requires the acquisition of numerous terms and special concepts necessary for the future specialist. But during the time allotted for the study of a foreign language at the University, it is impossible to master all the terminology, so it is very important to develop students' skills with special dictionaries, glossaries, reference books on the speciality [4].

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that The main reasons for the insufficiently high quality of teaching a foreign language, taking into account the professional specifics of a non-linguistic university, are not only a small number of hours allocated for

studying a foreign language, the lack of special training for foreign language teachers for non-linguistic faculties of universities, the low level of language education in secondary schools, but also the insufficient development of the methodology of teaching a foreign language in integrative connection with vocational training. The educational component of teaching in a foreign language consists, in our opinion, in the formation of students' respect and interest in the culture and the people of the country of the studied language; fostering a culture of communication; maintaining interest in learning and formation of cognitive activity; fostering the need for practical use of language in various fields of activity, including professional ones.

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